

7: Using Flies to Understand The Human Brain

Harvesting published data to power neurobiology research

How would you feel if you heard that our brain has many features in common with that of a fly? It may sound surprising, but the brain of a fruit fly replicates some aspects of our brain, which can be very helpful when studying human [genetics](#), [sleep](#), and [even disease](#). Fruit flies are considered as model organisms, i.e. organisms that have simpler systems but still approximate to our own. The advantages of model organisms are that they can be manipulated more easily and, in the case of flies, they have a short lifespan. This means that several generations of fruit flies can be studied in as little as a few months.

The Virtual Fly Brain repository

Studying the brain of a fruit fly is no easy task, mostly due to the insect's very small size. Scientists have developed different approaches to study these organisms, including [dynamically labelling neural connections](#), [imaging brain activity in moving flies](#), and [exploiting super resolution microscopy](#). However, these and many other efforts risk going unnoticed if their results are not gathered and organised for the sake of re-usability. This is what projects such as [Virtual Fly Brain](#) are doing, by integrating neuroanatomical and expression data from the published literature as well and image dataset onto a single brain template. It is a demanding endeavour due to the need to code existing data and make them suitable for sharing, but the researchers' goal is to make it easier for their peers to find relevant anatomical information

and reagents in the fruit fly's brain. The Virtual Fly Brain portal works as an open source [3D image viewer](#) that can be queried to find further information and images on a number of features of the insect's brain. The project is a compelling example of universities and funders collaborating to improve the effectiveness of data sharing and re-use. Partners include the University of Edinburgh, the University of Cambridge, the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), the Medical Research Council, and Northern American institutions in the [FlyBase Consortium](#) (Harvard University, Indiana University, and the University of New Mexico).

A 2012 [academic article](#) referencing the Virtual Fly Brain project has already garnered more than 20 citations, indicating that the portal is increasingly recognised as a useful resource in the field of fruit fly neurobiology.

What are the benefits of studying fly brains?

Fruit fly neurobiology is a diverse research field and there are multiple uses for information generated on the topic. For example, mapping patterns of individual neural connections in fruit flies may lead to greater understanding of the communication that occurs between individual synapses in the fruit fly brain. This research can be applied to humans and will assist researchers in developing increased awareness of how the human brain processes information. Other interesting research is focused on the [circadian regulation of sleep behaviour](#). It is thanks to fly genetics that we now know the molecular logic of circadian clocks, and further research on the

topic will allow us to explore the links between sleep and learning at the molecular level.

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Subtitle	Harvesting published data to power neurobiology research
Abstract	Studying the brain of fruit flies is helping researchers uncover how our brains work at the molecular level. Data repositories such as the Virtual Fly Brain help them curate, share, and re-use data in a structured way.
Keywords	neurobiology; medicine; fly; brain;
Research subject area	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
Type of RDM impact/benefit	Reproducibility; Efficiency in research and data re-use (e.g., reduce duplication of effort)
Summary Impact Type	N/A
Facts and figures	
Original dataset from which the impact arose	
Maturity of the initiative/data source	Long-standing (5+ years)
Year (e.g., first data release, first output, year of impact)	2012
Organisations involved	University of Cambridge; University of Edinburgh; Medical Research Council; EMBL-EBI
Academic citations	Milyaev, N., Osumi-Sutherland, D., Reeve, S., Burton, N., Baldock, R. A. & Armstrong, J. D. (2012). [The Virtual Fly Brain browser and query interface](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btr677). <i>Bioinformatics</i> 28, 411-5.
Links	https://helix.northwestern.edu/article/why-fruit-fly-research-no-joke http://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms10024 http://www.nature.com/nmeth/journal/v13/n7/abs/nmeth.3866.html https://doi.org/10.3389/fncel.2016.00142 http://www.virtualflybrain.org/site/vfb_site/home.htm http://flybase.org/ http://www.neurobiology.northwestern.edu/people/core-faculty/ravi-allada.html